

“What is so crucial about growth,
that makes it so indispensable to
society despite its impossibility? ”

A mapping exercise on why growth remains a core slogan
...and.... Is it possible to map strategic ways out?

How to lay down the underlying logics and dependencies and discuss about strategy in a visual way?

Defenders of the Nature, or alarmed researchers on the impact of biodiversity loss make their voices loud to preserve resources that are essential to many human activities – or hold an intrinsic value that needs to be preserved as such. But investments are still low and actions reflect the place environment holds in priority ranking – certainly not the top ranks, for citizens and governments alike, despite some changing. There seem to be more important issues to tackle, like ensuring economic growth. “Green” will not pay the bills, will it? Moreover, it seems essential at first look that economic growth makes environmental policies (among others) even possible, by providing capital and financial resources, or even security for basic needs, that allows to free the mind for environmental issues, still often seen as luxury concerns. Even SDGs place goal nr 8 – sustained economic growth, as a suitable essential factor for a better future.

In the perspective of the present crisis, even fundamentals of this credo in economic growth seem to shake. Is this the right time to question it and discuss alternatives not only as a theory, but as a strategy ?

Myths

Large groups, large producers have more power, have all advantages so we ought to imitate them

More CO₂ means plants grow better

More technology is better

Small producers, big producers, consumers, all distributors ... all have the same interests

« others » are evil and liars

Climate change is global warming. It just means that it will get a bit warmer (2 degrees? Pah, like 35 instead of 33 in summer? Ridiculous! Who cares!)

The starting point, several articles on the environmental aspect of the economic logic of growth, GDP and affluence. And a bunch of myths that have already been debunked, but still stick (*Industrial agriculture feeds the world - Industrial agriculture is the only way to avoid famine - The productivist model brings prosperity to those who follow it - Taking care of the environment is something we cannot afford to do – or sthg we do once all the rest has been done - More is better - We need to preserve our way of living at all costs - Consuming will save the world, if the world consumes « green things » - Personal initiative is central (vs systemic transformation)*)

First step, the productivity paradox in a visual way: what are the questions we ask? With what means do we analyse it?

References:

Productivity paradox – (*missing reference....*)

Scientists' warning on affluence – T. Wiedmann, M. Lanzen, L.T. Keysser, J.K. Steinberger – Nature communication, 2020

CO₂ ou PIB, il faut choisir – présentation août 2019, Sciences Po, Dr. J Jancovici

Can the world get along without natural resources? Blog article from economicsfromthetop.com, by Blair Fix, 18/06/2020

Reset Sustainable Development Goals for a pandemic world, Nature 583, 198-201 (2020)

Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K. *et al.* A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature* **461**, 472–475 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1038/461472a>

A Safe and Just Space for Humanity: Can we live within the doughnut?; Kate Raworth – OxfamGB, 13 February 2012

The usual question: Is this farm (system) profitable?

The usual answer: look at the indicator:

On farm level, (extended to globalized context)

Efficiency/productivity = Yield/unit input

Or

profitability=benefits-costs

If the numbers are right, (the balance on the benefit side),
it is profitable/efficient/productive

→ It is suitable

→ push planning, innovation, investments towards
intensive, industrial agriculture

The usual question: Is this profitable?

→ push planning, innovation, investments towards intensive, industrial agriculture:

- Intensification (surface and human productivity increase)
 - High yields at low prices, use of « enhancers » (fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides,..)
 - Focus on « cash crops » and « high performing » varieties
 - Function based on large, increasing monocultures with low personal, high technology management
- Landscape simplification, natural space fragmentation

→ *On the long run, on large scale* → (what we observe)

- « cash crops » are often high-calory-low nutrients;
 - High amounts of additives (pesticides, hormones,...) to increase productivity
- effects on **health** = cost

- Landscape simplification, monoculture and intensive agriculture
- effect on **environment**, loss of environmental services =cost

- Low prices → rebound effect
- **waste** increase = cost (and overall efficiency loss)

The next question: Is this system still profitable if those costs are to be included?

Is this system still profitable? Playing with numbers.....

If, as growing evidence shows, the health, environmental and other costs increase, the system might not be as profitable as it seems, two answers are possible: change system, or follow the logic, and diminish costs. It is important to keep in mind that some costs are often not directly accountable/accounted for, as they are hidden (indirect, only after some time, etc.). Often, they are carried by other places or times, or measurable only on a larger scale. However, there is here a good motivation to deliberately shift the highest costs (towards society in general, other countries or simply, more vaguely, the future...) to keep the balance positive.

Strategy, with such a perspective, remains a shell trick with numbers, depending on what to include and monetize in which way.

Is this system profitable?

But, more importantly, the presentation in this form It has perverse effects:

- The connection between profitability and suitability.
- The blindness for mechanisms, including backfiring mechanisms of soil fertility or pollinator loss, investment race, price fluctuations, etc.
- The desperate search for a way to reduce costs or increase gains at any cost (!!), because it is still the only metric.

The wrong question: balancing benefits and costs. This overly simplified representation is misleading, as it represents a farm as a independent system, influenced only by what is quantifiable financial gains and losses. The profitability, and suitability depends on an accounting system and allows high costs in one domain to be acceptable if balanced by gains in others, as they are measured all by the same metric. No question about « unacceptable » consequences, quantifiable but irremediable (irreplaceable) losses...

Shifting from : « *Is this system profitable ?* »
to « *Is this system suitable ?* »
Decoupling profitability from suitability

First of all, the factors are intertwined: certain practices increase or decrease costs, health is a gain or a cost depending on the practice; environmental degradation causes a loss in environmental services, different inputs can improve or worsen health impacts, etc.

Second, some costs are often not directly accountable for, as they are hidden. On a global scale, it is not honest to hide or dismiss them to promote the very same system causing them. → the **inter-dependence** of the different factors is **not shown**, even if it's essential to really evaluate the losses and benefits on a global scale. So, even if including costs in the balance is a useful step, it is still not helping to draw solutions and strategies, or understand what is missing in the equation.

Therefore, finally, non directly quantifiable costs as cultural heritage, biodiversity losses are arguably not meant to be counted in financial costs, or balanced against them, as high profit could justify these losses. If financial costs are the only metrics, a balance can justify irremediable health, cultural or natural losses, if the profit is high enough.

Shifting from : « *Is this system profitable ?* »
to « *Is this system suitable ?* »
Decoupling profitability from suitability

By only looking at a balance, it is nearly impossible to draw a strategy or a way out of the industrial, latifundist agricultural logic.
Even well-meant actions of lowering the environmental impact, using less harmful pesticides, or campaigns to reduce waste can lose their potential impact if they are not part of a whole strategy that includes acting on the very causes of those effects.

It can nevertheless serve as one instrument of measure for some factors, debunk some myths about cost effectiveness, and give an incentive for a new way of looking at things:

Starting with the question

« Is this way of working and calculating still efficient/profitable if the real costs on society are taken into consideration? »

It puts the accent on society:

As a farm cannot be responsible individually for this kind of complex, holistic calculation and for the consequences on health and the environment, it is time to shift the question towards the society as a whole.

We could argue that, indeed, it is a systemic productivity and efficiency that is to be aimed at:

$$\text{Total system efficiency} = \frac{\text{\#people fed healthy and sustainably}}{\text{unit input}}$$

...to follow up...

Going further – finding new means of understanding the way of functioning

How can a world with finite resources grow indefinitely? Physically, mathematically or biologically it is clearly unachievable, but it still remains a scope. What is so crucial about growth, that makes it so indispensable to society despite its impossibility? Why is it so difficult to conceive a way of functioning that changes this logic? While it is still understandable to imagine the motivations for industries, firms or big companies to follow this credo, it is less obvious why citizens, or governments would support it. Even the sustainability goals include growth in their objectives (SDG nr 8).

I decided to map the intrinsic logic of the hegemony of growth, in particular from a state's/government's perspective. The aim is to visualize the dependencies in place, show some consequences of certain choices and doctrines, define hurdles toward a sustainable future, and to present a document to discuss possible paths.

Links between citizens and industry from government perspective

Citizens in working age are either workers or unemployed, almost all citizens are consumers. The government ensures social services as healthcare, unemployment benefits and other benefits. It needs a budget, paid partly by taxes from citizens.

Industry does production, with capital and workers, using technical and natural resources. It also pays taxes. Capital can be a firm per se and could pay taxes from capital (or not). Consumers consume a generic production produced by a generic term called industry.

This is overly simplified, because industry is not one big logical entity. It does not differentiate between life essentials and other consumptions. Consumers can also consume from own production, small local private producers, big producers, public producers, national and foreign producers, industry that delocalizes a part of production. This change in description will be crucial to develop an alternative strategy. But anyway, the logic demands an increased production within a quantifiable market! (free production of goods and services is not quantified!!) → draw fluxes!!

The map shows straightforward need chains between stakeholders, practices and concepts with a logical link. We can base this links on the point of view of the government.

So, the government needs voters among the citizens to get to power and to pay taxes.

There is big interest to increase capital from industry/capital side (how to show this on the map?). Government has interest to keep income coming and voters. What is the government's logic?

Logic of growth from government's perspective:

Gvt needs income – from taxes (1). Taxes come from working citizens and industries (some part also capital) (2). Unemployed citizens receive additional social services (unemployment)(3). So gvt needs working citizens at producing industries (4). Additionally, citizens are also consumers; working citizens have more income and can curb consumption and therefore curb production. An additional interest of the government is to keep industry's capital within the own borders, to benefit taxes (?). So it has interest to keep up production and consumption, so capital would not move abroad. A crisis shifts the working citizens into the unemployed fraction, reducing the state's income and increasing its spending. A demographic crisis or simply demographic transition increases the share of non-working population and the corresponding social expenses (3b). As for now, the only strategies left are to cut social services to reduce costs, and to raise consumption, give tax cuts to capital to keep it within borders. Increasing pensioning age, or shifting response to crisis towards individual initiatives are other responses to the same logic and vision of the reality.

Links between citizens and industry from government perspective

However, industry needs resource, technical as well as natural resources: an ever-growing consumption from an ever-growing production means an ever-growing tapping into the natural resources (5). This seemingly small detail on the map is however an essential point to show the dependency of the whole from those resources!

Indeed, natural resources still are, however, according to the liberal logic, abundant, and “free”, even more since the blind reasoning between productivity and GDP assigns them a neglectable share in “richness production” ...
 Now, even if this point is rather easy to make, it shows the vicious effects of reasonings based on pure GDP accounting.

But the logic behind keeping a sufficient share of the population working instead of being a cost to society, and to keep capital from industry within its borders obliges governments to embrace this futureless logic. There are therefore other dependencies to debunk to imagine a system working in a different way.

Is there another strategy that a government can embrace without compromising its primary mission, and to keep its society “within the donut”?

As a map is only a model, it is lacking a lot of information. Thus, to make it useful, it needs to contain all the useful, relevant information for strategy.

So the first steps towards strategy is to question the rightful place of all present elements on the map (maturity), and then decompose elements into what is meaningful for the question, and add maybe missing parts.

First, where does the flow start, what is the original source? What is the driver?

What are the assumptions that need to be mapped better in order to be challenged in a constructive way?

The threat of moving capital outside borders; the cost/expense logic of a state; the quantification of income and services, not accounting for “free” services; the definition of working; the lack of ultimate explicit goal (the government is merely a accountant of expenses and costs?), the flow of gains (where does the state place its “gains” and “losses”; how can a state be rich and so many within be poor?); the complexity of industry and capital (obligations towards capital, towards an international banking/trust/grading system); the flow of energy/material/chem.elements/social well-being or whatever is useful to picture the real exchanges (does it trade capital investments against social welfare, trading efficiency with environmental preservation) ; where to show the underlying doctrines? Where do they play? Name them and show them on a map to walk the strategy path...

Can we show on the map that the “ever lasting growth” is not only breaking environmental sustainability, but not even up to the promise of guaranteeing social well-being??

Should it all be the consumers’ responsibility? What motivates a shift in businesses taking actions? What can policy makers change? What do consumers or voters accept?

In a government’s perspective, choosing between priorities, to satisfy not only voters but also a wide range of other stakeholders, is a difficult balance exercise.

First, what is a government's role? In theory, its mission is to maintain coherence in society and provide life-sustaining services to citizens: *institutions of the government* :
'regulate the relationships among members of a society and between the society and outsiders'
and that they 'have the authority to make decisions for the society'
to meet goals
and maintain order

In the first map we drew, the government's role was shown from the regulative side of citizens' income and own balance between expenses and income, but in a system out of its control.

However, a government is also able to take decisions, maintain order and meet goals.

Digging deeper into the government's role and its legitimacy, the growth logic tells to prioritize income-bringing activities [for the one applying it], whatever the environmental cost, which can also cause important social costs. Especially if the cost cutting logic suppresses social services, social troubles are very likely – as reality already shows. As crisis come and go, and growth without regulating elements causes inequalities, the government can choose to maintain order through increasing police controls and repression, or smoothing discourses. The alternative is to place regulating mechanisms to counter accumulation, promote redistribution and thus lower inequalities, which smoothens tensions. Same applies to regulating the relationships among members of the society.

But the real question is: who sets the goals? Following fear-induced decisions imposed by its potential « capital shifters », as suggested in literature, does imply the goals are set by owners of the capital. If so, capital is governing and government is maintaining the order and buffering the costs where possible, shifting them to its citizens.

Does the government have other resources? Who is it officially representing?

It can take decisions: so it's its responsibility if certain paths are followed over others. It has the power to decide to tax, privatize, nationalize, prioritize expenses, invest in infrastructure, subsidise certain stakeholders to achieve goals.

Environmental management can be drawn from government's perspective: the government needs voters to get to power and to pay taxes. Specific, targeted taxes are not well defined or less spread, or even inexistent.

For environmental issues, the connection between voters and their needs are not clear: status, romantic nostalgia, general well-being, cause to defend, or research specialty. To simplify, we call it fulfillment, to differentiate it from survival needs. This class of voters might not be a majority, but since this movement is gaining momentum, it is somehow important to care for the environment (i.e. natural resources) to get these voters satisfied. So nature conservation and sustainable practices – which might be financing research projects - would be a response. This needs some form of technical resources to implement.

It also depends upon a budget, handled by a ministry of environment from the government, financed partly by taxes.

But if global voters care for nature per se is still relatively low, taxes are low and budget is low, too. Practices are likely not much developed.

Public health in an universal healthcare system

Are there current practices that base their investment of people, time, finances on other logics?

Let's take the example of public, universal health care system. As previously, the government needs voters to get to power and to pay taxes

Voters need to survive, hence their need for health. Health itself is sustained by healthcare in form of treatment, facilities and preventive care.

All those need a budget, handled by a ministry of health from the government, payed partly by taxes from voters. For treatment, natural resources might be used. Technical resources are needed for treatment, facilities and preventive care.

These links are very strong, as they are linked to survival.

Simplified map of the public health care system (adapted from Wardley maps, p 356, fig 239)

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These links are very strong, as they are linked to survival feeling (and reality), unlike environmental causes, that are more perceived as a noble initiative. As fulfillment can be reached by many other means, it can be reasoned that, unlike health (survival), caring for the fulfilment of its citizens is not a government's priority role.

What makes this system a good (or bad?) choice, and why would a government choose a public, universal healthcare system, while other countries' governments choose the logic of growth for the same human activities? What is the strategy behind? Is it a different context? A different reasoning about the same situation? Are there just different stages of maturity of the system? Is a system under development more able to develop under a private individual management, and a public universal healthcare system a sign of a mature stage, where a though of global efficiency, standard service, where error is not expected? On the other hand, is maximizing efficiency not the logic of growth, leading to poor resiliency and a wild running logic of a physically impossible path?.....?

But as a system matures, disruption comes when "war" happens ... because of limitation of resources. "Salvation" comes from a groundbreaking change in either techniques or practices, or both. It is an uncertain path, as it is not possible to predict future changes. Nevertheless, it is possible to predict certain shortages and the need for a new way of functioning.

What if the links and the flows changed? From universal to private or the opposite?
 How to draw the strategy?

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Starting with survival (“essential”) activities, the provision of food could be a candidate, too. Why is healthcare imbedded in a wide network of public providers, guaranteeing a service geographically uniform and covered, with a common standard, and not food? Food is mostly provided everywhere, with a “standard” defined by chains of providers and national or international laws.

The government’s responsibility in a universal healthcare system is to make sure anyone who needs that care gets it.

Is it the government’s role to make sure ppl CAN BUY food or DO HAVE food? Is it the government’s role to make sure farmers (some farmers? The farmers with the loudest voice?) have an income or do produce to feed all citizens in a healthy way? Financial social services or coverage of material needs? Not to say that these are mutually exclusive, but the prioritization draws the path and the consequent choices.

Food system in a universal food security system

A system where food, or at least the basic, vital food needs, would be provided as part of a universal program, with providers, facilities and staff: SECUAL

Farmers as public employees ...Or subdued to a worse system? As medical doctors, they fulfill certain standards to become certified providers. Who decide those criteria and what could they look like? How many should be compulsory and which ones could be an additional motivation and trigger? Does this pose a threat to be hijacked to exclude sustainable production? Would a mafia-like system be able to evolve from this?

It is important to raise this questions, and to make sure the conditions and stakeholders are clear beforehand, and to design the system in a way to avoid, or make uninteresting, such drifts.

One hint would be to link it to the social protection system (in countries where it is functioning). Indeed, social system overload is also connected with voters' income linked to taxes or unemployment. Not to forget that social system have been successfully established precisely in times of critical economical situations.

A Safe and Just Space for Humanity

Can we live within the doughnut?

Publication date: 13 February 2012

Author: Kate Raworth, Senior Researcher, OxfamGB

The doughnut: “a visual framework – shaped like a doughnut – which brings the concept of planetary boundaries together with the complementary concept of social boundaries, creating a safe and just space between the two, in which humanity can thrive.”

In the doughnut doctrine, GDP is no longer a metric of success and growth is a factor breaking the environmental ceiling, while not necessarily guaranteeing the social foundation

Source: Oxfam, inspired by Rockström et al (2009)

If we change the questions (doctrine/imperatives) , and re-orient the fundings, we can also change the attractive/promoted gains

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Preserve your way of life.

No cost is too high.

Buy efficiency and high yield, contribute to GDP growth and get exonerated from health and environmental costs!
Bonus included: substantial public support!

Buy food resilience and good health, contribute to societal change and reduce health and environmental costs for your children!
Bonus included: substantial public support!

BE INDIANA JONES,
discover old treasures and new adventures!

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Preserve landscape, culture, diversity. Preserve life.

No path is too steep.

Example of response: “the farmers need income”+ “logic of growth provides income” + “growing GDP is necessary to keep capital and get a good grade in international credit system” → keep increasing productivity, increasing GDP, compensate price decrease with destruction of produce, subsidy farmers to compensate for losses in income.

Doctrine	Choices and implementation	Results (sought after)	(unintended) consequences
<p>“the farmers need income” “logic of growth provides income” “growing GDP is necessary to keep capital and get a good grade in international credit system”</p>	<p>keep increasing productivity→ increasing GDP compensate price decrease with destruction of produce subsidy farmers to compensate for losses in income.</p>	<p>Farmers have income for the season, GDP is safely increasing Farming industry is proudly productive Investments in more technology to increase productivity is justified</p>	<p>Food waste Loss of sense of farmers Financial trouble of framers who cannot keep up with investments necessary to increase productivity Risk of environmental, health and social cost Cost of financing destruction</p>
<p>Eliminate costs</p>	<p>Shift costs: Social costs: unemployment benefits, financial support Shift to illegal workers Develop industry of environmental purpose: recycling, remediation etc. (increase GDP) Shift to other countries</p>	<p>Keep income minimal for (precarious) workers Works gets done Environment is taken care of (health aspects) with focus on impact attenuation</p>	<p>Hidden social cost Hidden (long term) environmental costs Fertility decrease of soil Long term loss of resilience</p>

Example of response: “the farmers need income” + “all people need to eat sufficient, healthy food” + “resources are what they are, they need to be preserved for long term” → focus on needs (nutrition), acknowledge limitations, regulate, organize production and distribution on the long term

Doctrine	Choices and implementation	Results (sought after)	(unintended) consequences
<p>“the farmers need income” “all people need to eat sufficient, healthy food” “resources are what they are, they need to be preserved for long term” (“doughnut doctrine”)</p>	<p>Guarantee minimal production Guarantee variety Support sustainable practice SECUAL Set standards for quality</p>	<p>Farmers who seek after reconversion are supported Sense of worth in own work (recognition of contribution to society) Investments in more sustainable practice is supported</p>	<p>Less production, possible loss in productivity Crisis in transition phase Investments of past become obsolete, a financial burden Risk of social cost GDP decrease</p>
<p>Minimize (long-term) costs</p>	<p>Include all costs in price: Social costs: unemployment financial support Avoid shift to illegal workers Count industry with environmental purpose: recycling, remediation etc. as a cost (temporary investment to reset) Transform cost in investment (support for transition) Empower locals</p>	<p>Keep minimal income for workers Price depends on complying to doughnut doctrine Environment is taken care of (health aspects) with focus on regeneration</p>	<p>Hidden (long term) environmental mitigation Societal changes</p>

Cf thoughts on SECUAL